

Honorable Custos, distinguished Opponent, ladies and gentlemen.

A contemporary German humanist, Werner Herzog, has directed a documentary entitled *Grizzly Man*. *Grizzly Man* is a modern, Aesopian animal fable telling the true story of Timothy Treadwell, who lived for thirteen summers in Alaska with the bears and said to protect the bears, to love the bears, to be like a bear until a bear finally ate him and his girlfriend in 2003. Herzog's documentary is based on hundreds of hours of actual footage that Treadwell himself shot and narrated during his time in Alaska. Recurring themes in the documentary are the distinction between the animal and human world, man becoming a bear and an individual being alone in the wild. The main theme, however, in the documentary is self-preservation and how Treadwell is said to risk his own life in order to protect the life of the bears. One question that emerges is whether he is crazy in doing so.

Is preserving life in one form or another the defining feature of humanity? This might be the morale of *Grizzly Man*, but it is not the sole motivating principle of human actions. Is it crazy to risk one's life for some seemingly futile cause? If we risk our lives, are we necessarily doing it for the cause itself or for ourselves? At the end of this lectio praecursoria, I will give a Mandevillean interpretation of the *Grizzly Man* based on the idea that self-preservation is not the defining feature of human existence. Before that, we need to explain how this interpretation is constructed.

I

My doctoral dissertation is entitled *Self-love and self-liking in the moral and political philosophy of Bernard Mandeville and David Hume*. The main argument concerns the role of pride in David Hume's philosophical system and his account of the conjectural development of civil

society. With conjectural development, or conjectural history, I refer to a sociological and psychological account of the progress of civilization. What I claim to do is to offer a new interpretation of artificial moral institutions for Hume and how it affects our reading of the role of morals and politics in Hume's science of man. I claim to do this partly by showing the relevance of a neglected concept, greatness of mind, in Hume's thinking. The most important aspect of greatness of mind for Hume is that it is directly linked to self-liking, which we will consider first.

II

A key figure in my doctoral dissertation is Bernard Mandeville who actually coined the term self-liking. Mandeville was a Dutch medical doctor, who emigrated to London at the turn of the eighteenth century, perhaps as a political refugee, and lived there for the rest of his life. Mandeville also worked as a translator, translating for example La Fontaine's animal fables into English.

Importantly, I claim, we can detect a change in Mandeville's thinking. In his later life Mandeville wrote books that intellectually ought to be considered independent of his notorious *Fable of the Bees*. Mandeville started out as a polemist, but later he turned into an original social theorist. This could not have happened without a revision of his views. Mandeville developed a hypothesis where justice and politeness are explained as decisive, artificial moral institutions based on previous human conventions. Crucially in my understanding, the later Mandeville is not attempting to defend the view he previously set forward. Instead he started asking different questions.

According to my interpretation, the later Mandeville detaches himself from Hobbism that reduced all human actions to self-love and self-preservation with the claim that fear is the main element that civilises men. The idea in Mandeville's later works is to nurture the passions, not to suffocate them. This is the same strategy that Hume employs in his *Treatise*. The key-move (that both Mandeville and Hume employ) is to accept some other-regarding affection out of which parental affection towards one's children is the prime example. It is noteworthy that later Mandeville characterises this natural affection as a pure and durable passion. Without any selfish motives, parents can be said to love their children. The significance of this is that it brings out the possibility of discussing fully natural virtues, for example, kindness towards any living creatures, including animals such as bears. What this also indicates, is that we cannot simply ignore Mandeville by labeling his moral system utterly selfish, hedonist or egoistic.

The second move was to introduce a new concept: self-liking. Mandeville signifies that self-liking consists of two components. Firstly, 'nature has given' men 'an instinct, by which every individual values itself above its real worth'. Secondly, this natural instinct is aligned with 'an apprehension' of the fact 'that we do over-value ourselves', which 'makes us so fond of the approbation, liking and assent of others; because they strengthen and confirm us in the good opinion we have of ourselves.'¹ These definitions ought to be seen in the light of the French neo-Augustinian tradition and Pierre Nicole's writings in particular.

Since we have to separate self-love and self-liking in their own spheres – and this also concerns Hume's *Treatise* – we can show how to draw justice and politeness from corresponding passions. Justice guards our self-love. It has much to do with self-preservation and it enables us to cultivate our interest. This is the sphere of life, limbs and

¹ *Fable*, II, p. 130.

private property. At the same time, politeness is the moral institution that enables us to cultivate our self-liking. The idea is that the passion itself is responsible for the corresponding moral institution. The geometrical simplicity of this is quite striking. Now the idea is to cultivate the passions and not to curb them. The best instance of this is politeness and the popular idea in early modern Europe that we need to hide our pride. We all are naturally proud, the pride of others hinders our pride, therefore we need to be proud without showing it to others. This creates a positive cycle of cultivating our self-liking by developing different ways of pleasing others and not showing what we actually think of ourselves.

III

According to my interpretation David Hume is fully aboard Mandeville's ship. Firstly, Mandeville is pointed out as one of Hume's predecessors in the introduction to Hume's *Treatise*. Secondly, the story of conjectural history of civil society (and justice and politeness) in the third book of the *Treatise* is partly a verbatim copy of Mandeville's later works. And thirdly, Hume fully commits himself to Mandeville's scheme of the distinction between self-love and self-liking in all of his works.

In a section of the Book 3 of his *Treatise of human nature*, also crucially entitled 'Greatness of mind', David Hume explained for the first time that the symmetric passions of self-interest and pride are only to be controlled by the corresponding moral institutions. In the case of self-love or self-interest, the corresponding moral institution is justice. Respectively, concerning self-liking or pride the moral institution is politeness. There is an explicit analogy between these moral institutions.

In his later *Enquiry concerning the principles of morals*, Hume repeated the argument in these words:

‘As the mutual shocks, in *society*, and the oppositions of interest and self-love have constrained mankind to establish the laws of *justice*; in order to preserve the advantages of mutual assistance and protection: In like manner, the eternal contrarieties, in *company*, of men’s pride and self-conceit, have introduced the rules of GOOD MANNERS or POLITENESS; in order to facilitate the intercourse of minds, and an undisturbed commerce and conversation. Among well-bred people, a mutual deference is affected: Contempt of others disguised: Authority concealed: Attention given to each in his turn: And an easy stream of conversation maintained, without vehemence, without interruption, without eagerness for victory, and without any airs of superiority. These attentions and regards are immediately *agreeable* to others, abstracted from any consideration of utility or beneficial tendencies.’ (EPM, 8.1. p. 67)

The relevance and implications of the idea expressed in this passage are of central importance when interpreting Hume’s moral and political thought. What we need to see in particular are the further implications of the distinction between self-love and self-liking for Hume’s political thinking. As a consequence, we learn the importance of the necessary connection between science of man and politeness, civilised monarchies, social distance and the hierarchical structure of civil society.

One way to grasp the relevance of the distinction between self-love and self-liking is with a reference to greatness of mind, which is a disposition that underpins the centrality of pride. Although greatness of mind is a broad concept, it can be defined. Greatness of mind is Ciceronian in its origin and Hume’s conception of it stood in contrast with the eighteenth-

century Christian ideas of greatness of mind. For Hume greatness of mind was a particularly modern disposition to fashion one's self, cultivate one's pride and in particular, a readiness to prefer pride over self-preservation. Greatness of mind can be said to be one of the main ingredients of the social theory of his *Treatise*. The concept is closely linked to self-liking that before Mandeville had no name in the English language. A further idea directly related to greatness of mind for Hume is to explain how modern European monarchies are the seed of gallantry and honour that makes the social and political life in them comfortable and explains how large societies can exist peacefully in great contrast with ancient republics.

In greatness of mind, agreeable comes before useful, ambition before avarice, outward show and greatness in appearance before actual humility and artificial principles before natural sentiments. Greatness of mind also includes a military dimension in the link between 'politeness', 'sense of honour', gallantry, 'courage' and 'martial skill'. Crucially, courage is not based on anger or self-love, but pride. Modern courage as an expression of greatness of mind was founded on artificial principles that functioned in accordance with pride. But most of all, Greatness of mind for Hume was 'a disposition or turn of mind, which qualifies a man to rise in the world'.

IV

Streamlining human nature and moral institutions in this Mandevillean manner gives an opportunity to analyse the development of civil society in a new way. Mandeville and Hume start with the idea of hypothetical state of nature, like many others, but instead of drawing conclusions about social contract or natural laws implemented by God, they tell

the story as a naturalistic, historical process of the moral institutions of justice and politeness.

When conjectural history is used as a methodological tool, it is possible to pay crucial attention to the differences between small and large societies. Since the dynamics of a small, family society is completely different from a large society, where not everyone is related or does not necessarily even know each other, this also implies that different factors hold these different kinds of societies together. Therefore the difference between natural and artificial virtues is all the more crucial. It is easy to explain how a small society remains intact based on natural principles, such as lust between sexes and familial affection. The large societies, however, need artificial moral institutions that supplement the lack of natural benevolence that we simply do not feel towards people who are unknown to us.

What is also important is that the Mandevillian use of the distinction between self-love and self-liking ends with an argument regarding universalism. The uniformity of human passions compels all human societies to form certain guidelines. These rules cannot be called natural in a sense that we could find them out by rational calculation or that to follow them would be natural for human nature. However, the process of forming these artificial guidelines always follows a similar path. Every civil society that is able to function will have developed institutions of justice and politeness in one form or another. Without these two (and only two) different moral institutions large societies simply cannot function. One could of course think of many other artificial virtues, which are formed in the same sense. However, because of human nature, theoretically the argument is that only justice and politeness are the necessary ingredients of every functioning civil society.

I promised a Mandevillean explanation to the *Grizzly Man*. As we recall, the definition of self-liking consisted of two parts: an instinct to over-value one's worth and a need to confirm our opinion of ourselves by the approval of others. Before Mandeville and Hume, Pierre Nicole made a similar analysis of pride. Nicole's conception of the desire of being loved is particularly useful for us to analyse the *Grizzly Man* from the Mandevillean perspective.

Timothy Treadwell's story in Hertzog's documentary is reversed compared to similar stories in the eighteenth century. Some Enlightenment accounts of true stories consider individuals being raised in the wild and then later entering the human society. The image of *Grizzly Man*, instead, is someone leaving the human society and integrating into the world of animals. In reality, Timothy Treadwell never left the human world. His audience followed his vanity where ever he went.

According to Nicole, the reason why we desire to be loved is simply 'that we may love our selves more'. The point is that we need support for the good opinion that we have of ourselves.² Our opinion of ourselves is laid on such a vulnerable ground that it cannot sustain itself without being under-propt by the approbation and love of others.³ Hence, all that our desire of being loved has to do with is our pride.

Timothy Treadwell was an actor by profession. He was not very successful before he left for Alaska and started his life with the bears. One cause of pride according to Hume is that the cause needs to be related to the self, it needs to be constant and most of all it needs to

² Nicole, *Moral essays*, II, p. 233. Nicole, *Essais de morale*, II, p. 126.

³ Nicole, *Moral essays*, II, pp. 233-4. Nicole, *Essais de morale*, II, p. 127.

be peculiar to ourselves. Crucially, also for Hume, pride cannot be sustained without an audience, but even an imaginary audience will do. When something is recorded on film, the idea of an audience is easily present. But the matter is not as simple as to say that Treadwell merely wanted success and approval. Even from a Mandevillean perspective, there is no need to doubt that *Grizzly Man* also sincerely loved the bears and believed that he protected their lives at the risk of his own. Yet, a Mandevillean explanation suffices perhaps better than the simple comment that he was crazy because of risking self-preservation. The *Grizzly Man* was somewhat eccentric, but as an incarnation of modern Aesopian fable, he also serves as a fine epitome of human nature that escapes definitions based solely on the conception of self-preservation.

When judged from the perspective that underlines social cohesion in a secular world, there is a positive, natural effect of the fact that ‘we must be flattered and caressed like children’ or ‘in our fashion we fall crying, as children do in theirs’, as Nicole writes. It is crucially the insecurity of the opinion of ourselves that makes us want other people’s approval, which, more often than not, renders us sociable. And as David Hume says, the true bond of union among men is not self-love or self-preservation, but our vanity.

Dr John Robertson, I now call upon you to present your critical comments on my dissertation.